

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Best practices

[SMART WEST]

SPOKE 4 – DIGITAL INNOVATION TOWARD SUSTAINABLE MOUNTAIN

DELIVERABLE 5

This document is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – M4C2 1.5 of PNRR funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU (Grant agreement no. ECS00000036).

Summary

In an era of rapid technological evolution and profound social changes, remote working has emerged as one of the most fitting responses to the challenges of modern work. The pandemic has accelerated this transition, pushing organizations and employees to quickly adopt more flexible work arrangements, transforming home spaces into work environments. However, this sudden shift has also highlighted various issues, such as the lack of structured planning and the isolation of employees.

This deliverable on best practices is presented as a white paper that deeply explores the dynamics, opportunities, and challenges of remote working. Given its purpose, the deliverable was written primarily in Italian to make it more accessible to entrepreneurs and workers in the NODES area. However, this English document provides a summary of the work done and a translation of the table of contents.

These guidelines provide a comprehensive framework for understanding and implementing effective strategies in today's work environment. The white paper is organized into chapters, each of which can be read sequentially or independently, allowing readers to access relevant information based on their needs.

The main document (Deliverable_5_1) aims to be a useful resource for anyone looking to navigate and succeed in the modern work landscape, addressing the challenges and maximizing the opportunities offered by remote working. Below is a summary of the main content covered in the various chapters.

In the next chapter, the concept of agile work is analyzed, focusing on organizational and legal aspects. Special attention is given to the Italian regulatory framework, highlighting the importance of training for both employees and managers, and the role of collective bargaining in improving the balance between work and personal life.

The second chapter shifts focus to hybrid work from a sociological perspective. It discusses the risks of isolation, the importance of the right to disconnect to prevent burnout, and the new inequalities arising from this work mode, particularly those related to gender and occupational sectors.

In the third chapter, the challenges and opportunities of remote working for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Italy are examined. The impact of remote working varies depending on

company size and sector, with particular attention paid to cybersecurity challenges and the need for technological investment.

The fourth chapter covers performance management in remote working. It explores how organizational culture needs to evolve, placing more emphasis on accountability and flexibility. Performance measurement tools based on Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are introduced, along with the Activity-Based Costing (ABC) method to help optimize resources in SMEs.

In the fifth chapter, the focus is on workspaces and employee well-being in relation to the physical and social environment. It discusses the psychological and environmental implications of remote working, highlighting the challenges of blending home and work environments and the importance of maintaining in-person relationships. Design approaches such as Biophilic Design and Restorative Design are introduced to enhance the quality of workspaces.

The sixth chapter examines the technological tools needed for the effective implementation of remote working. Topics such as cybersecurity, collaboration, and mobility are covered, with a focus on emerging technologies that can support agile work and ease the challenges of managing remote work.

In the seventh chapter, attention shifts to European funding instruments and the opportunities provided by the European Union to support digital transformation and the adoption of remote working. The chapter outlines key funding programs, both direct and competitive, with a focus on those promoting innovation and digitalization.

The final chapter summarizes the study's key conclusions, emphasizing that remote working is not only an opportunity but also an organizational and social challenge. Recommendations are proposed for promoting a more equitable and sustainable implementation of this work mode, with a particular focus on cybersecurity, continuous training, and employee well-being.

In addition to the main document, two separate appendices are available, providing deeper insights into the guidelines. Appendix A (Deliverable_5_2) contains a literature review on the topic in English, while Appendix B (Deliverable_5_3) provides a chronological overview of qualitative interviews conducted with companies during the project in 2023 and 2024.

In conclusion, the deliverable offers a comprehensive and multi-dimensional view of remote working, highlighting the numerous benefits and challenges it entails. Through historical analysis, reflection

on its advantages and difficulties, and an examination of best practices and future prospects, a complex and dynamic picture emerges, underscoring the importance of adapting agile work to the specific needs of organizations and employees.

The successful implementation of remote working depends not only on adopting the right technologies but also on fostering a corporate culture that promotes flexibility, communication, and well-being. Organizations must be prepared to invest in their human capital and establish clear policies that protect workers' rights while ensuring an inclusive and productive work environment.

In a constantly evolving world, remote working represents a significant opportunity to rethink how work is done, fostering a more sustainable and responsible approach. It is essential for companies and professionals to continue exploring, adapting, and innovating their practices to meet future challenges successfully. We hope this document helps facilitate these changes, particularly in the context of economic, social, and environmental sustainability.

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